

USE OF ELEMENTS OF WRESTLING TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the factors of using elements of wrestling in improving the effectiveness of physical education in primary school.

INTRODUCTION At present, the task of reforming the education system in the country, the organization of classes in primary education at the level of modern and non-traditional needs is urgent [1]. In this regard, it is important to organize physical education classes in addition to traditional methods in forms based on modern, technological and non-traditional principles. Because physical education classes in primary school are organized mainly in the traditional way, in which the main attention is paid to the correct formation of children's physical behavior.

METHODOLOGY In fact, physical education classes in primary school should focus on:

- formation of children's physical characteristics in a correct and medically appropriate way;

- development of children's musculoskeletal system in accordance with their age and mental characteristics;
- physical training of children;
- Introduce students to children's sports at an early stage. All this requires the organization of physical education classes in the primary grades on a new basis. Relying on non-traditional training methods for this will yield the expected results.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS The widespread use of national wrestling sports in physical education classes helps to increase the effectiveness of physical education classes. Wrestling is organized taking into account the set of existing conditions, factors and opportunities [2]. In this regard, it would be expedient to develop mechanisms for the use of national wrestling in the organization of physical

education classes in primary school. According to our approach, the main aspects of these mechanisms are:

1. Consideration of opportunities. At the same time, in order to organize physical education classes in primary school with the widespread use of national wrestling sports, attention is paid to: - the school's ability to conduct physical education classes at the required level; - professional training of teachers conducting physical education classes at the school; - The existence of conditions for the combination of theoretical and practical concepts in physical education. It is the availability of these opportunities that will be the basis for the organization of training through national wrestling sports. 2. Organization of physical education classes at a modern level. To do this, it is necessary to: - organize physical education classes in a way that is focused on their development, based on the physical and mental characteristics of primary school students; - Conducting physical education classes covering all types of children's sports; - The formation of the ability of students in any type of children's sports in physical education; - Achieving the orientation of students to children's sports as a result of physical education. This approach increases the effectiveness of physical education classes.

3. Organization of physical education classes in cooperation with national kuash clubs and leading specialist coaches of the Republican BOSM. If there are two factors mentioned above to organize the use of wrestling in the national sport in order to increase the effectiveness of physical education in the primary grades, then it is advisable to organize training in

collaboration [3]. To do this, it is expected that: - with the help of specialists to give students a clear idea of the national sports and their importance; - Regular training of students in children's wrestling with the help of specialists; - Involvement of talented students in wrestling with the help of specialists; - direct a relatively large percentage of physical education classes to get acquainted with national sports; - more organization and holding of national wrestling competitions at school; - Assess the development of students' interest in physical health and sports as a result of training based on the elements of national wrestling [4]. It should be noted that the organization of physical education on the basis of our national sports has the potential not only to form our national ideology, but also to achieve the proper physical development of students and the formation of their physical health skills [5]. It should be noted that the organization of classes on the basis of the national sport of wrestling in physical education classes with primary school students requires some conditions and opportunities, but its practical effectiveness is important. At present, our secondary schools have the opportunity to hold physical culture and sports events, and school gyms are equipped to a modern level.

CONCLUSION The main task of the teacher is to organize the use of national wrestling sports in the development of physical education in the primary grades. To do this, the teacher must be aware of the elements, techniques and tactics of the national wrestling sport, the factors of its organization and ways to achieve effectiveness. Because the wide use of our national sports in education contributes to

the formation of patriotism and national young people. In this regard, in our opinion, it would be expedient to pay more attention to the wider use of national

pride in sports in increasing the effectiveness of physical education in the primary grades.

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